

Raman Amplifier Design and Launch Power Optimisation in Multi-band Optical Systems

ANDRÉ SOUZA^{1,2,*}, NELSON COSTA¹, JOÃO PEDRO^{1,2}, AND JOÃO PIRES²

¹ *Infinera Unipessoal Lda, Rua da Garagem 1, Carnaxide, Portugal, 2790-078*

² *Instituto de Telecomunicações, Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisboa, Portugal, 1049-001*

* *anunes@infinera.com*

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We propose an innovative optimisation framework using a multi-objective genetic algorithm to simultaneously optimise the launch power profile and design the Raman amplifiers. Its flexibility allows us to find better solutions and reduce the number of Raman pumps. Moreover, we utilize the framework to compare the potential of four multi-band transmission systems leveraging hybrid fibre amplification. Simulation results highlight that complementing a C+L-band system with the S-band leads to higher total system capacity than using the E-band or interleaving data channels and Raman pumps.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Multi-band transmission systems enhance the data-carrying capacity of optical networks. While spatial-division multiplexing (SDM) is often considered the most future-proof solution for increasing optical network capacity [1], there are valuable alternatives. We can broaden the available transmission spectrum by incorporating the longer (L-) and shorter (S-) transmission bands alongside the traditional C-band. It is important to note that multi-band transmission (MBT) and SDM are not mutually exclusive approaches [2]. In future optical networks, MBT will likely optimise transmission capacity per fibre, core, or mode, seamlessly complementing SDM to meet the ever-growing demand for capacity.

Commercial systems already incorporate the L-band, potentially doubling the total system capacity. Researchers actively explore systems with even wider bandwidth, focusing on devices compatible with transmission bands beyond the C- and L-bands. Leveraging the S-band, which shares similar fibre characteristics with the C- and L-bands, holds promise. Numerous studies have already shown the additional capacity made available by integrating the S-band into a C+L-band system [3–5].

Optimising the launch power is crucial for maximising the capacity of MBT systems. For instance, fine-tuning the average value and power tilt of transmitted channels in a 15-THz S+C+L MBT system enabled improving the generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR) from 0.6 dB to 1.6 dB [6]. However, this optimisation task is far from trivial due to several factors. It depends on the stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) effect, which cannot be neglected in MBT systems, the frequency-dependent characteristic of fibre parameters, and the unique features of band-specific devices such as optical amplifiers. Moreover, opti-

mising the launch power is a nonlinear problem. Recent publications have explored launch power optimisation in MBT systems using methods such as explicit enumeration [7, 8], iterative algorithms [5, 6], or genetic algorithms (GA) [4, 9].

Even after proper launch power optimisation, performance in the S-band is still worse than in the other two bands. This performance disparity primarily results from power transfer to the C- and L-bands, driven by the SRS effect. Additionally, higher fibre losses and potentially higher noise figures (NF) in S-band amplifiers contribute to the optical performance imbalance across transmission bands. Recent research indicates that selective Raman amplification can enhance S-band performance, bringing it closer to the levels observed in the C- and L-bands. This improvement simplifies service provisioning in optical networks that utilize MBT [5]. However, optimising Raman pumps remains challenging due to the nonlinear nature of the SRS effect. Various approaches have been proposed to tackle this issue. For instance, Yankov et al. [10] trained separate neural networks (NNs) to predict the Raman gain for forward- and backwards-propagating pumps, respectively. Then, they optimised the system using a gradient descent algorithm. It is worth noting that this approach relies on the accuracy of the NNs, and their training process may not be straightforward. Furthermore, dedicated NN models are necessary for each specific scenario [11].

Various single-objective evolutionary algorithms have been employed in this context. Among them, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) is one of the most popular choices for ensuring gain-flatness performance and bandwidth optimisation in multi-pump Raman amplifiers [12, 13]. Researchers have also proposed enhancements to the traditional GA, such as the hybrid-GA (HGA) optimisation procedure [14, 15]. Additionally, Jiang

Fig. 1. (a) Representation of optimisation variables and (b) multi-objective genetic algorithm framework.

et al. introduced the Ant Colony optimisation [16] and the Artificial Fish School Algorithm [17] to find optimal pump parameters, offering alternatives for designing gain-flattened Raman Fiber Amplifiers (RFAs). Another search method used in RFA design is Particle Swarm optimisation, known for its fast convergence and improved computational efficiency [18]. While previous studies often tackled the Raman amplifier design and launch power optimisation separately, this work proposes a framework that simultaneously optimises the launch power and the Raman pumps in MBT systems using a multi-objective GA approach.

Introducing the S-band in a C+L-band system poses challenges, as the optical power interactions caused by the SRS effect can affect existing services. An alternative approach is to bypass the S-band and utilize the E-band instead. Maintaining a guard band of 14 THz between the E-band and the operational C- and L-bands can prevent power transfer between the newly added and existing bands [19]. However, prior research has not fully explored the impact of using Raman amplifiers to enhance the performance of the C+L-bands. In this scenario, power loss in the E-band becomes significant due to high-power Raman pumps at lower frequencies. Our study compares the network performance across three configurations: C+L-, S+C+L-, and E+C+L-bands. These configurations employ hybrid amplification techniques, including fiber-doped lumped amplification and backward-propagating Raman distributed amplification, with each band occupying 6 THz of spectrum. We optimise channel powers and the design of the Raman amplifiers using a multi-objective GA, aiming to maximise system capacity while equalizing performance within each band. This work extends the analysis initially presented in [20] by incorporating the following features:

- Using a more accurate model of the SRS and the amplifier noise figure;
- Giving a detailed explanation of the optimisation algorithm and exploring the impact of its hyperparameters;
- Replacing one of the optimisation objectives that was detrimental to the performance of the E+C+L band system (equalization of the performance of all transmitted channels).

The work is organized as follows. The multi-objective optimisation algorithm is described in Section 2. Section 3 details the optimisation setup and the networks used to obtain the results

presented in this work. Afterwards, Section 4 presents and discusses the results and practical considerations when applying the algorithm to commercial networks. The study culminates in Section 5, where we summarize our research's key findings and conclusions.

2. OPTIMISATION FRAMEWORK DESCRIPTION

This work uses the per-channel GSNR as the quality of transmission (QoT) estimator (considering the signal bandwidth as a reference). This QoT metric is given by Eq. (1), where P_i is the power of channel i and P_i^{ASE} and P_i^{NLI} are the power of the Gaussian noise corresponding to the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise and the nonlinear interference due to the self- and cross-channel nonlinear crosstalk at channel i , respectively.

$$GSNR_i = \frac{P_i}{P_i^{ASE} + P_i^{NLI}}. \quad (1)$$

The optimisation algorithm aims to maximise the sum of the channels GSNR ($GSNR_{sum}$) and minimise the sum of the per-band GSNR variation ($\Delta GSNR^b$) of a MBT system considering hybrid amplification. $\Delta GSNR^b$ is given by the difference between the best and the worst GSNR considering all channels in transmission band b . Fig. 1a depicts a representation of the optimisation variables for a transmission system with three amplification bands and three Raman pumps. The proposed framework optimises the average channel power (P_b) [dBm] and power tilt (T_b) [dBm/THz] of each band, as well as the pump powers P_p^j . The algorithm considers that the candidate pumps have fixed frequencies (f_p^j).

There are two general approaches to multiple-objective optimisation. One is to combine the individual objective functions into a single composite function or move all but one objective to the constraint set. The second general approach is to determine an entire Pareto optimal solution set or a representative subset. The concept of a Pareto set of optimal solutions stands for a set of solutions that are non-dominated by each other but are superior to the rest of the solutions in the search space. A solution is called non-dominated if none of the objective functions can be improved in value without degrading some other objective values. Pareto optimal solution sets are often preferred to single solutions because, when considering real-life deployments, the final solution can involve a trade-off [21]. Therefore, we select

Fig. 2. (a) Telefónica national reference network diagram and (b) frequency spectrum of different transmission system configurations. From left to right and top to bottom: C+L, S+C+L, Int-S+C+L, E+C+L-band system.

145 the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) multi-
 146 objective GA to solve the optimisation problem due to its good
 147 level of convergence to the true Pareto Front and diversity [22]
 148 (the Python library Pymoo [23] was used).

149 Figure 1b presents the algorithm workflow. The algorithm
 150 starts from an initial population of P individuals randomly gener-
 151 ated from a uniform distribution. Each individual's chromo-
 152 somes represent P_b , T_b and P_p^j (float values). Before evaluating
 153 each individual's fitness, a repair function [23] guarantees that
 154 the sum of the pump powers is smaller than a given value (P_p^{TOT})
 155 for all generated individuals by normalizing the pumps powers
 156 if the total pump power is greater than P_p^{TOT} . Afterwards, the
 157 fitness of the individuals is evaluated according to:

$$F_1 = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}} C \left(\text{GSNR}_i - p \cdot \min(0, N_p - N_p^{MAX}) \right) \quad (2)$$

$$F_2 = \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \left[\Delta \text{GSNR}^b + p \cdot \min(0, N_p - N_p^{MAX}) \right] \quad (3)$$

159 where GSNR_i is the GSNR of channel i and $C(\cdot)$ is the ideal
 160 Shannon capacity of channel i (given by Eq. (4) [24], where R_S
 161 is the channel baud rate), \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{C} are the sets of amplification
 162 bands and channels, N_p^{MAX} is the maximum number of Raman
 163 pumps allowed, p is the penalty for every Raman pump exceed-
 164 ing N_p^{MAX} . The algorithm aims to maximise F_1 and minimise
 165 F_2 . Notice that these objectives are concurrent since the highest
 166 capacity of a given transmission system is achieved for a given
 167 value of GSNR variation [25, 26], and some system capacity must
 168 be sacrificed to equalize the GSNR further.

169 When evaluating the GSNR, the algorithm only considers
 170 pumps with powers higher than a certain threshold (P_p^{TH}).

$$C(\text{GSNR}_i) = 2 \cdot R_S \cdot \log_2(1 + \text{GSNR}_i) \quad (4)$$

171 Next, the offspring of the current population is generated via
 172 mating and mutation (N individuals). The same repair function
 173 used in the initial population corrects the offspring's chromo-
 174 somes, and the algorithm calculates their fitness. Afterwards, all
 175 individuals are sorted in Pareto fronts (PF_i) and according to the
 176 crowding distance. The P best individuals survive and are used
 177 for the next generation while all others are eliminated.

178 The value of the penalty (p) may change during the algo-
 179 rithm operation. For example, it may be set to zero for the initial
 180 generations. Hence, with an unbiased evaluation, the algorithm
 181 searches the entire solution space in the initial phase. It may be
 182 set to a different value afterwards, so the algorithm evolves to-
 183 wards solutions requiring fewer pumps. We chose to implement
 184 the penalization of the number of pumps exceeding N_p^{MAX} as a

185 GSNR penalty for simplicity of the analysis. This way, having
 186 the same p value for both fitness functions independently of the
 187 transmission system is possible. For example, if we apply a fixed
 188 penalty value outside the summation in F_1 instead of inside $C(\cdot)$,
 189 it would have different effects in transmission systems with dif-
 190 ferent numbers of channels (higher penalization in systems with
 191 lower channel count/total capacity and lower penalization in
 192 systems with higher channel count/total capacity). The same
 193 effect happens for F_2 , but the difference applies to systems with
 194 different numbers of transmission bands. Additionally, F_1 and
 195 F_2 would require different p values because of the magnitude
 196 difference between the total capacity and the sum of ΔGSNR^b .

197 Different fitness functions (F_i) may be defined if other optimi-
 198 sation objectives are considered more important. For example, if
 199 a flat GSNR profile is desired across the entire transmission win-
 200 dow instead of a per-band flatness, ΔGSNR^b may be switched
 201 to ΔGSNR in the fitness function F_2 , where ΔGSNR is given by
 202 the difference of the best and the worst GSNR of all transmitted
 203 channels (similarly to what we did in [20]). Another possible
 204 development of the optimisation framework is to include the
 205 number of Raman pumps as an objective to be minimised. For
 206 example, a third objective may be included with $F_3 = N_p$ and
 207 p set to zero in F_1 and F_2 . This way, the algorithm finds the
 208 Pareto front representing the trade-off between the highest cap-
 209 acity, lowest per-band GSNR variation and lowest number of
 210 pumps. However, this solution involves including an additional
 211 objective. It could lead to higher convergence times and poorer
 212 optimisation performance (other evolutionary algorithms, such
 213 as the NSGA-III [27], may perform better than the NSGA-II in
 214 this case). Therefore, one should keep in mind the convergence
 215 and practicality of the fitness functions; F_1 and F_2 are good exam-
 216 ples of fitness functions in the sense that they allow for a good
 217 convergence performance while also allowing for the limitation
 218 of the number of Raman pumps used. This enables the analysis
 219 of the trade-off between the number of pumps, system capacity
 220 and per-band GSNR flatness.

221 3. SIMULATION SETUP

222 To give a glimpse of the optimisation algorithm's utilization and
 223 give examples of its usefulness, we evaluate the performance of
 224 the different MBT approaches in the Spanish national reference
 225 network, as defined by Telefónica in the IDEALIST project [28]
 226 (Fig. 2a), considering, for simplicity, a fully loaded spectrum
 227 and that all spans are 80 km long. The number of 80-km spans
 228 in each link is given by $\lceil L_l/80 \rceil$, where L_l is the link length in
 229 kilometres and $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ is the ceiling operator. The Spanish national
 230 network has 30 nodes and 435 shortest paths between nodes,

Fig. 3. Frequency-dependent fibre loss and nonlinear coefficient.

Fig. 4. Normalized Raman gain profile.

with an average length of 834 km and an average link length of 261 km. The optical fibre is modelled by a nonlinear coefficient of $1.27 \text{ W}^{-1}/\text{km}$, a dispersion parameter of $16.8 \text{ ps}/\text{nm}/\text{km}$, and a dispersion slope of $0.058 \text{ ps}/\text{nm}^2/\text{km}$ at 1550 nm. The frequency-dependent loss and nonlinearity coefficients and the normalized Raman gain profile of the optical fibre are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. Additionally, input and output connector losses of 0.25 dB and splice losses of 0.01 dB/km are assumed. After each fibre span, a band demultiplexer (with a 1 dB insertion loss) separates the transmitted bands and delivers them to the respective optical amplifier. We consider a band demultiplexer based on a band filter and assume its insertion loss will be slightly higher than current commercial C+L-band filters [29]. The lumped optical amplifiers are modelled by a constant noise figure of [6,6,7] dB for the L-, C-, and S-bands for gain values larger than 20 dB. For gain values smaller than 14 dB, the amplifiers' NF is 2 dB higher. The NF is linearly interpolated for gain values ranging between 14 and 20 dB. Their gain compensates for the loss of each channel, considering the impact of the SRS effect and the gain already provided by the Raman amplifiers. The power evolution of the signals and pumps across the fibre is calculated by numerically solving the Raman differential equations (using the solver available in GNPY [30]). Subsequently, the transmitted bands are recombined by an optical coupler (with a 0.5 dB insertion loss).

We consider the transmission of 120-Gb/s (R_S) signals in a 150-GHz spectral grid (40 channels per band). Fig. 2b shows the four MBT system configurations considered in this work. All sys-

Table 1. Required OSNR (defined in 0.1 nm) for each considered bit rate.

Bit rate [Gb/s]	400	500	600	700	800
$OSNR_{req}$ [dB]	18.7	21.0	23.5	25.0	26.5
SNR_{req} [dB]	8.9	11.2	13.7	15.2	16.7

tems employ up to 10 counter-propagating Raman pumps with 1 THz spacing and a minimum guard band of 500 GHz between adjacent bands. First, as a reference scenario, we consider a C+L-band system with channels from 184.5 THz to 197 THz and pumps from 199 THz to 208 THz. Then we have two versions of the S+C+L-band with channels from 184.5 THz to 203.5 THz and pumps (i) from 205 THz to 214 THz and (ii) from 199 THz to 208 THz. The first system is called the S+C+L-band system (this MBT system will be the focus of this work due to its good optical performance, as will be shown in Section 3.B), whereas the second is called the Int-S+C+L-band system. In the Int-S+C+L MBT system, the Raman pump and S-band channels are interleaved. We considered a guard band of 500 GHz around the pumps to avoid signal degradation [31], reducing the number of channels on the S-band from 40 to 21 in this scenario. Lastly, we consider an E+C+L-band system by adding the E-band, from 211 THz to 217 THz, to the reference scenario. The frequencies of the E-band channels were selected to maintain a guardband of 14 THz from the C-band channels, as suggested in [19]. In this case, it was considered that the NLI interference caused by the E-band on the C- and L-bands is negligible and vice-versa; therefore, the NLI was calculated separately. The Raman amplifier is assumed to add an equal amount of noise on both polarizations. All transmission systems use the same band demultiplexer and coupler. This allows upgrading the C+L-band system by adding a new transmission band without disrupting running traffic.

The multi-objective genetic algorithm optimises the power of the channels and the pumps. The initial population size of the GA is 120, and 60 offspring are generated at each generation, $P_p^{TH} = 50 \text{ mW}$ and $P_p^{TOT} = 1 \text{ W}$. The algorithm ran until convergence of the hypervolume performance metric [23]. The number and frequencies of the Raman pumps and the maximum total pump power values are selected here just to illustrate the algorithm's utilization. These values correspond to a good trade-off between execution time and capacity of GSNR flattening. Note that an arbitrary number of pumps and pump frequencies can be defined, and the algorithm will converge to the optimal maximum total pump power and distribution of the available power among the pumps.

After optimisation, we evaluate the number of feasible lightpaths and the network-wide average system capacity [32] in the Spanish national network. The five different bit rates considered in this work and their required OSNR and SNR are presented in Table 1. These values were taken from the OpenRoadm agreement [33] for 200 Gb/s, 300 Gb/s and 400 Gb/s formats and scaled up from 64 Gb/s to 120 Gb/s to represent a near future optical MBT system (500 Gb/s and 700 Gb/s values were linearly interpolated). The SNR_{req} values are directly calculated from the $OSNR_{req}$ values using the relation given in [34], i.e., $SNR_{req} = OSNR_{req} - 10 \log_{10}(R_S/B_{ref})$, with B_{ref} equal to 12.5 GHz.

For each channel, the GSNR at the end of a lightpath with N

Fig. 5. Non-dominated solutions after convergence and best solution using the iterative algorithm for the S+C+L-band system.

spans is given by $GSNR_N = GSNR - 10\log_{10}(N) - M$, where $GSNR$ is the optimised per-channel and per-span GSNR and M is the system margin defined as $M = 2 + 0.05(N_{OLAs} + N_{ROADMs})$. This margin comprises a fixed 2 dB margin and a variable contribution that depends on the number of traversed optical amplifiers (N_{OLAs}) and ROADMs (N_{ROADMs}). Additionally, we consider a transceiver OSNR of 38 dB and add/express OSNR of 38 dB/37 dB. A lightpath is feasible for a given signal configuration if the required SNR is smaller than $GSNR_N$.

The network-wide average system capacity metric is used to estimate the impact of the performance of the different transmission systems at the network level. The average system capacity is the sum of the network-wide average channel capacity [32] for all transmitted channels. The average channel capacity is the value of the highest feasible bit rate of a channel, averaged for all the shortest routing paths of the network.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Raman Pump Count

A.1. Fixed Raman Pump Penalty and Variable Pump Limit

In this section, we show how N_p^{MAX} may be used to influence the Raman pump count on the solutions and compare the performance of the proposed framework with an iterative approach based on the weighted sum method [6] in an S+C+L MBT system. The latter uses a fixed number of pumps (2 pumps) to compute results in a reasonable time frame. Following the same approach as in [35], the iterative algorithm considers pump frequency separations from 1 to 8 THz in steps of 1 THz, and pump power profiles where the optical power of the highest frequency pump is 1, 2, 3 and 4 times higher than the lowest one. It also imposes a maximum total pump power of 1 W. In the GA simulations, N_p^{MAX} is set to 1, 2, 4 or 10 and $p = 2$ (in Eq. (2) and Eq. (3)).

Figure 5 shows the Pareto fronts after convergence and the solution found by the iterative algorithm in terms of the total ideal system capacity, which is obtained by the sum of $C(GSNR_i)$, and the average $\Delta GSNR^b$ for an 80-km span. By comparing the Pareto fronts, we conclude that using higher N_p^{MAX} leads to flatter GSNR profiles for a given system capacity. However, the highest achievable total capacity remains mostly unchanged, i.e., it is only slightly dependent on N_p^{MAX} , ranging from 137.3 Tb/s for $N_p^{MAX} = 1$ to 138.8 Tb/s for $N_p^{MAX} = 10$. Note that this result is also a consequence of setting a maximum total pump power of 1 W, independently of the number of used pumps. The Pareto fronts are similar for N_p^{MAX} equal to 4 or 10. The front

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. Raman pump power (in mW) distribution for GA solutions with an average $\Delta GSNR^b$ of (a) 2.7 dB and (b) 0.7 dB for the S+C+L-band system.

for $N_p^{MAX} = 2$ is close to the previous two for average $\Delta GSNR^b$ values higher than 2.3 dB, but the difference becomes significant for lower per-band GSNR variation values. By reducing N_p^{MAX} to one, the solutions have higher average $\Delta GSNR^b$ for the same capacity. For example, the GA with $N_p^{MAX} = 1$ achieved a minimum of $\Delta GSNR^b = 0.7$ dB at a total ideal capacity of 124 Tb/s. In contrast, the same average $\Delta GSNR^b$ is achieved with total ideal capacities of 131, 134 and 135 Tb/s for N_p^{MAX} equal to 2, 4 and 10, respectively.

The behaviour of the Pareto fronts results from the number of Raman pumps used. To further clarify this point, Figs. 6a and 6b show the pump power distribution for the GA solutions for an average $\Delta GSNR^b$ of 2.7 and 0.7 dB, respectively, for each value of N_p^{MAX} . For an average $\Delta GSNR^b$ of 2.7 or 0.7 dB, the solutions use 1, 2, 4 and 10 pumps for N_p^{MAX} equal to 1, 2, 4 and 10, respectively. Moreover, all solutions of the Pareto fronts have a Raman pump count equal to or smaller than N_p^{MAX} . Therefore, using lower N_p^{MAX} effectively reduces the number of Raman pumps and may lead to a more cost-effective solution.

For a high value of average $\Delta GSNR^b$, the GA converges to solutions that use almost all the allowed power for the Raman pumps. The sum of the pump powers shown in Fig. 6a are 967, 997, 999 and 1000 mW for N_p^{MAX} equal to 1, 2, 4 and 10. On the other hand, the sum of the pump powers to achieve a lower GSNR variation (shown in Fig. 6b) are 213, 953, 991 and 996 mW for N_p^{MAX} equal to 1, 2, 4 and 10. Solutions with a single pump tend to have a smaller total pump power when minimising the average $\Delta GSNR^b$ because it is harder to get a flat profile with only a small number of pumps, i.e., a single high-power Raman pump would cause a high GSNR variation within a band. On the other hand, using more pumps allows for a better distribution of the available power and a flatter GSNR profile while using a high total pump power.

Moreover, to gain more insight into the impact of using different numbers of Raman pumps, Figs. 7a and 7b show the

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. (a) Launch power and (b) corresponding GSNR profile for GA solutions with an average ΔGSNR^b of 2.7 dB for the S+C+L-band system.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8. (a) Launch power and (b) corresponding GSNR profile for GA solutions with an average ΔGSNR^b of 0.7 dB for the S+C+L-band system.

389 optimum launch power and the corresponding GSNR profile,
 390 respectively, for the solution leading to $\Delta\text{GSNR}^b = 2.7$ dB. As
 391 expected, since the total ideal system capacity is very similar
 392 for the 4 considered cases, the launch power and, consequently,
 393 the GSNR, values are very similar regardless of the number of
 394 Raman pumps used. On the other hand, if we aim at a low
 395 average $\Delta\text{GSNR}^b = 0.7$ dB, whose corresponding results are
 396 depicted in Figs. 8a and 8b, the curves for N_p^{MAX} equal to 4 and
 397 10 are very similar whereas reducing N_p^{MAX} causes a reduction
 398 in the average GSNR, particularly in the S- and C-bands. This
 399 result highlights that using more Raman pumps is an effective
 400 approach to improve the average GSNR while still keeping the
 401 per-band GSNR variation reduced.

402 Looking back at Fig. 5, we see that the iterative algorithm
 403 converges to a solution similar to the Pareto front with $N_p^{\text{MAX}} = 2$.
 404 This similarity is expected since the same number of Raman
 405 pumps is used. However, the iterative algorithm only converges
 406 to a single solution. On the other hand, the proposed framework
 407 offers a broader set of solutions, e.g., with higher average GSNR
 408 (at the cost of a higher per-band GSNR variation) or smaller average
 409 ΔGSNR^b (at the cost of also worse average GSNR). Moreover,
 410 the iterative algorithm also took longer to reach a solution, even
 411 with a limited set of Raman pump counts, profiles, and channels
 412 power tested. Both algorithms were implemented in Python and
 413 ran in a single 2.2-GHz core. The iterative algorithm took an
 414 average of 8 hours to run the optimisation, whereas the GA only

415 required an average of 5 hours.

416 A.2. Influence of the Raman Pump Penalty Value

417 Because of the value of p used in the previous section ($p = 2$),
 418 all solutions of the Pareto fronts presented have a Raman pump
 419 count equal to or smaller than N_p^{MAX} . However, the algorithm
 420 may converge to solutions with more pumps than N_p^{MAX} for
 421 lower Raman pump penalty values, potentially leading to better
 422 performance results.

423 Figure 9a shows the Pareto fronts after convergence for an
 424 80-km span and a S+C+L MBT system for different values of
 425 p and $N_p^{\text{MAX}} = 1$. The figure shows that reducing p improves
 426 the Pareto fronts by relaxing the requirement of using a single
 427 Raman pump. In the limit, i.e. for $p = 0$, the algorithm behaves
 428 exactly as when $N_p^{\text{MAX}} = 10$, yielding the best results.

429 Carefully selecting the Raman pump penalty value allows ob-
 430 taining solutions that perform better at the cost of having more
 431 pumps than N_p^{MAX} . Fig. 9b shows the Raman pump count for
 432 different values of p versus the average ΔGSNR^b . The improve-
 433 ment in the system capacity observed in this case for the same
 434 average ΔGSNR^b when compared with the previous results is
 435 due to using more Raman pumps. The best solutions are found
 436 when $p = 0$, i.e., when there is no restriction on the number of
 437 Raman pumps used in the solutions (up to 10 pumps may be
 438 used). For higher values of p , the solutions tend to use fewer
 439 Raman pumps and perform worse. For example, for an average
 440 $\Delta\text{GSNR}^b = 0.7$ dB, the solution on the Pareto front when $p = 2$

Fig. 9. (a) Optimal non-dominated solutions and (b) Raman pump count as a function of the average ΔGSNR^b of solutions for the S+C+L-band system.

Fig. 10. (a) Optimal non-dominated solutions and (b) Raman pump power (in mW) distribution for selected solutions for different transmission systems.

441 achieves 124.5 Tb/s with a single pump. For $p = 0.25$, the total 468
 442 capacity increases to 131.5 Tb/s with two pumps; for $p = 0.1$, 469
 443 the total capacity is 133.6 Tb/s with four pumps; and for $p = 0$, 470
 444 the total capacity is 135.3 Tb/s with ten pumps being deployed. 471
 445 In summary, the Raman pump penalty p controls the algorithm's 472
 446 flexibility to search solutions which may not be limited to N_p^{MAX} , 473
 447 thus allowing to find better-performing solutions for each region 474
 448 of the Pareto front. 475

449 B. S-band- vs. E-band Upgrade Performances

450 In this section, we perform a performance comparison between 478
 451 four MBT systems (C+L, S+C+L, Int-S+C+L and E+C+L) with 479
 452 $N_p^{MAX} = 10$. In our previous publication [20], we have shown 480
 453 that the optimised performance of the S+C+L-band system is 481
 454 superior to the E+C+L in terms of higher total ideal capacity 482
 455 and lower GSNR variation. However, the performance of the 483
 456 E+C+L-band systems was penalized by one of the optimisation 484
 457 objectives. In that work, we tried to equalize the performance 485
 458 of all bands while maximising the total ideal capacity of the system. 486
 459 However, because of the much lower performance of the E-band 487
 460 compared to the S-band (mostly due to the power depletion that 488
 461 the E-band suffers because of the Raman pumps), the performance 489
 462 of the C- and L-bands was penalized in the E+C+L-band 490
 463 system to enable the optical performance equalization. Instead, 491
 464 we revisit the problem using the objective functions (F_1 and F_2) 492
 465 described in Section 2. Therefore, one of the objective functions 493
 466 is still similar to the one used in the previous work, i.e., we aim 494
 467 at maximising the total ideal capacity of the system, but instead of

aiming to equalize the performance of all transmitted channels, 468
 now we aim at equalizing the performance of all channels within 469
 the same transmission band only (i.e., to minimise ΔGSNR^b). 470

Figure 10a illustrates the non-dominated solutions the opti- 471
 misation algorithm achieves upon convergence for each trans- 472
 mission scenario for an 80-km span. Among these solutions, 473
 the baseline C+L-band system is the least favourite solution re- 474
 garding total ideal capacity because of the reduced number of 475
 channels. Still, the system achieves the lowest average ΔGSNR^b 476
 value. As references, a maximum total ideal system capacity of 477
 98 Tb/s is achieved for an average ΔGSNR^b of 1.8 dB, whereas 478
 the minimum ΔGSNR^b of 0.2 dB is obtained for a total ideal 479
 system capacity of 88 Tb/s. 480

The S+C+L MBT system stands out as the top-performing one. 481
 It attains the highest total ideal system capacity of 139 Tb/s while 482
 maintaining an average ΔGSNR^b of 3.5 dB. It is worth noting 483
 that the average ΔGSNR^b can be reduced to as low as 0.3 dB with 484
 a 7% reduction only in total system capacity (down to 129 Tb/s). 485
 Thus, the S-band upgrade results in an increase of approximately 486
 47% in total ideal system capacity, when compared to the C+L- 487
 band system, while preserving the same average ΔGSNR^b (for 488
 ΔGSNR^b values varying from 0.3 to 1.8 dB). 489

The E+C+L-band and Int-S+C+L-band systems rank as inter- 490
 mediate solutions. The E+C+L-band system achieves smaller 491
 average ΔGSNR^b values, while the Int-S+C+L-band system 492
 achieves a slightly higher total ideal capacity (but also with a 493
 higher GSNR variation). The E+C+L-band system can provide 494

Table 2. Per-band average and variation of the GSNR (in dB) for MBT in one 80-km span for the selected solutions.

Band	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	vii	viii
L	30.4±0.1	31.8±0.8	27.7±0.4	28.9±2.0	30.4±0.2	32.0±0.9	27.8±0.5	27.7±0.2
C	25.8±0.4	29.6±1.8	29.1±0.2	31.2±1.1	29.5±0.7	30.3±1.8	27.5±0.4	27.5±0.6
S	-	-	24.3±0.1	27.1±2.1	22.2±0.2	25.1±3	-	-
E	-	-	-	-	-	-	17.1±0.3	17.6±1.2

21% more capacity than the C+L system at the same average ΔGSNR^b . The performance of the E+C+L-band system is smaller than the Int-S+C+L-band system due to the lack of Raman amplification to improve the E-band's performance, as well as the adverse impact of deployed Raman pumps, which, while enhancing the C- and L-bands, deplete the power of the E-band channels. For example, the span loss experienced by the central frequency of the E-band under the highest capacity solution of the C+L-band system is approximately 35 dB when Raman pumps are active and 24 dB when switched off. To alleviate this effect, some Raman pumps may be added in the higher frequencies (around 230 THz) to amplify the E-band. However, the higher attenuation reduces the amplification efficiency and increases the costs of such a system, so we leave this analysis for future work. Lastly, the Int-S+C+L-band transmission scheme exhibits intermediate performance between the C+L and S+C+L-band systems. This can be attributed to the smaller number of channels in the additional band and the absence of Raman amplification to enhance its performance.

Figure 10b presents the power levels of the Raman pumps for the eight optimised solutions identified in Fig. 10a, each representing the best outcome in one of the two objectives for each transmission configuration. Solutions i and ii refer to the C+L-band system, iii and iv to the S+C+L-band system, v and vi to the Int-S+C+L-band system, and vii and viii to the E+C+L-band system. Interestingly, in the Int-S+C+L-band system, very little power is allocated to some pumps with the same frequency as the S-band. Consequently, the capacity of the Int-S+C+L-band system could be enhanced by eliminating specific pumps and utilizing the available bandwidth for data transmission, which was not considered in this work. Furthermore, the algorithm converged to solutions that use very limited Raman amplification in the E+C+L-band system. The total pump power is 148 mW and 74 mW for solutions vii and viii, while it equals [750, 1000, 898, 999, 927, 1000] mW for solutions i to vi. The low Raman amplification on the E+C+L-band system reduces the total system capacity by approximately 13% when compared to the S+C+L-band system, even though they have the same number of channels.

Lastly, we compare the network performance of the selected solutions on the reference network. Table 2 details the per band average and variation of the channels' GSNR after transmission along a single 80 km span. The C+L-band system achieves the highest average GSNR. Interestingly, even though there is a 14-THz guard band between the end of the E-band and the start of the C-band in the E+C+L-band system, the optimised configuration of the three-band system has a lower average GSNR on the C+L-bands. This can be explained by the different Raman pump configurations in the two- and three-band systems. In the three-band system, the algorithm converges to solutions that use some power on the high-frequency pumps (higher or

Fig. 11. Number of lightpaths working at a given bitrate for selected solutions.**Table 3.** Network-wide average system capacity (in Tb/s) for selected solutions.

i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	vii	viii
53.0	60.5	75.0	84.1	68.1	72.8	55.1	56.0

equal to 205 THz) and reduce the power of low-frequency pumps (smaller than 205 THz) to reduce the power depletion of the E-band. Moreover, the E-band is the band with the lowest average GSNR, showing a degradation exceeding 7 dB in the average GSNR compared to the S-band in the S+C+L-band system.

The GSNR values presented in Table 2 are used to obtain the per-channel GSNR at the end of the lightpaths and calculate each transmission system's channel capacity. Fig. 11 shows the number of lightpaths operating at a given data rate averaged over all channels. For example, for each channel, some of the 435 possible lightpaths are feasible with the 800 Gb/s data rate, others with 700 Gb/s and so on. These quantities are averaged for all transmitted channels and presented as stacked bars in Fig. 11. When all lightpaths are feasible for all channels at least at the lowest bitrate, the bars stack up to 435, the total number of possible lightpaths in the network (only considering the shortest paths). However, if some lightpaths are unfeasible for some channels, the stacked bars do not reach this value. The highest number of unfeasible lightpaths occur in the systems with the E-band due to its low GSNR (available GSNR of approximately 17 dB only). The most spectrally efficient system (i.e., using more high bit-rate lightpaths) is the C+L-band system, thus confirming that adding more bands with worse fibre and amplifier characteristics harms the system's spectral efficiency. The Int-S+C+L-band system has a higher spectral efficiency than the S+C+L because of the higher GSNR on the L-band and the

572 smaller channel count on the lower-performing S-band. How- 631
 573 ever, the Int-S+C+L-band system has a lower network-wide 632
 574 average capacity because of the smaller number of channels, as 633
 575 shown in Table 3. Upgrading the C+L-band system by adding 634
 576 the E-band did not improve the capacity by much. In some cases, 635
 577 It even reduced the average network-wide system capacity. 636

578 C. Practical Considerations

579 There are some points of concern when applying the proposed 637
 580 optimisation algorithm in commercial networks. First, the av- 638
 581 erage run time of five hours for optimising a single span (as 639
 582 indicated in Section A.1) may lead to prohibitively long network 640
 583 optimisations. The reason is that networks like that presented 641
 584 in Fig. 2a have tens of different spans (with different lengths 642
 585 and other physical characteristics), and the algorithm would 643
 586 have to optimise each span independently. Second, more real- 644
 587 istic models for lumped amplifiers will alter the algorithm's 645
 588 performance. 646

589 Parallelising the calculation or reducing the time required 647
 590 for a single-span optimisation is needed. One may use sim- 648
 591 plified NLI estimation methods to reduce the QoT calculation 649
 592 time [36, 37]. Calculating the stimulated Raman scattering effect 650
 593 may be sped up by resorting to NNs [10]. However, training 651
 594 these NNs to predict the Raman gain for forward and backwards- 652
 595 propagating pumps is not straightforward and dedicated NNs 653
 596 are needed for each specific scenario [11]. Furthermore, both 654
 597 strategies (simplified NLI calculation and NNs for Raman gain 655
 598 prediction) lead to a decrease in the accuracy of the calculation of 656
 599 the GSNR. Therefore, there is a trade-off between optimisation 657
 600 time reduction and the accuracy of the results that should be 658
 601 considered. Alternatively, optimisations or NLI/Raman Gain 659
 602 values for fully-load conditions may be pre-computed for var- 660
 603 ious spans and system configurations for end-of-life network 661
 604 operation. Additionally, the GA parameters may be optimised 662
 605 to accelerate its convergence. 663

606 By employing more precise models for the various compo- 664
 607 nents of the transmission system, the system margin (M) can 665
 608 be reduced, thereby enhancing the network's capacity. Key com- 666
 609 ponents include the transceiver, fibre, lumped amplifiers, and 667
 610 reconfigurable add-drop multiplexers. The optimization frame- 668
 611 work's performance, as proposed in this work, is affected by 669
 612 the characteristics of the fibre and lumped amplifiers. A notable 670
 613 improvement in the lumped amplifier model used here is in- 671
 614 corporating a more realistic, non-flat noise figure profile that 672
 615 varies with the amplifier's gain. This realistic noise figure intro- 673
 616 duces additional GSNR variation, potentially making it more 674
 617 challenging for the optimization algorithm to find solutions with 675
 618 ΔGSNR^b values as low as those presented in this work. This 676
 619 analysis is deferred to future research. 677

620 5. CONCLUSIONS

621 We proposed and described a novel application of multi- 682
 622 objective genetic algorithms to optical communications: simulta- 683
 623 neously optimising the launch power and designing backward 684
 624 Raman amplifiers. The framework's operation and the effects 685
 625 of the hyperparameters on the the number of Raman pumps in 686
 626 the final solutions are demonstrated in an S+C+L-band system 687
 627 with hybrid amplification. Moreover, it is shown that the opti- 688
 628 misation algorithm may be used to find solutions with different 689
 629 trade-offs between the number of Raman pumps, total system 690
 630 capacity, and average per-band GSNR variation. 691

632 Our research has significant implications for network per- 633
 634 formance. We comprehensively compared four MBT systems: 635
 636 C+L-, S+C+L-, Int-S+C+L- and E+C+L-band systems, each utilis- 637
 638 ing hybrid amplification. Our findings indicate that the S-band 639
 640 upgrade for a C+L-band system is the most favourable choice 641
 642 when considering Raman amplification. This preference is a 643
 644 consequence of the SRS impact on the E-band. Indeed, Raman 645
 646 pumps deplete the optical power and, thereby, diminish the per- 647
 648 formance of the E-band, while enhancing the C+L-band system 649
 650 performance. 651

652 Although introducing additional transmission bands reduces 653
 654 spectral efficiency due to the less favourable fibre and ampli- 655
 656 fier characteristics of the additional bands, the cost overhead of 657
 658 deploying new fibres may still make these solutions competi- 659
 660 tive. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that interleaving Raman 661
 662 pumps with data channels in the S-band is disadvantageous for 662
 663 the system's total capacity. This disadvantage is primarily due 663
 664 to the resulting smaller channel count in the S-band, which is 664
 665 not compensated by a significant increase in the transmission 665
 666 system's spectral efficiency. 666

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